

Self-healing bacterial concrete exposed to freezing and thawing associated with chlorides

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Abstract

Recently, researchers have focussed on the development of self-healing strategies in order to guarantee high performance regarding the durability of concrete structures. Exposing self-healing concrete to extreme conditions and evaluating its behaviour is the first step in understanding how the self-healing mechanism performs under these conditions. Nevertheless, there are limited studies subjecting self-healing concretes to harsh conditions combining extreme low temperatures and salt attack. Therefore, we concentrate in this study on freezing and thawing conditions with de-icing salts, specifically with sodium chloride. It is an innovative assessment of self-healing concrete including commercially manufactured bacteria as healing agent. The objective is to ensure that autonomous crack healing occurs, restricting chloride ingress, extending the service life, and reducing the effect of degradation. The study presents the influence of the exposure conditions through permeability tests, microscopic investigations, scaling analyses, and chloride penetration. The permeability tests showed complete sealing after freezing and thawing cycles. Nevertheless, the healing products were removed together with material that was scaled off the surface due to cyclic freezing and thawing. The bacteria enhanced the properties of the concrete, resulting in less scaling and chloride penetration. However, chloride penetration through the crack cannot be prevented.

Keywords: Self-healing bacterial concrete, Freeze-thaw, Chlorides.

Introduction

The efficiency of self-healing concrete has been reported multiple times in literature showing the great potential of this technique to heal cracks. However, many of these studies were performed under ideal exposure conditions. Therefore, knowing how the self-healing concrete resists extreme conditions is extremely important to transfer this technology to practice. There are different self-healing mechanisms and several extreme conditions that need to be studied in depth. Hence, it will be possible to design structures with the most suitable self-healing mechanism for each extreme condition. A combination of cold temperatures and salt attack represents a realistic condition prevailing in cold countries which results to damage noticed in infrastructure such as highways, bridges, bike paths, ports, etc. There are two different types of deterioration due to freezing and thawing: internal cracking due to freezing and thawing cycles [1][2], and surface scaling, generally due to freezing in the presence of de-icing salts [3][4]. The cyclic freezing and thawing can produce a high pore pressure related to the water phase change inside the pores leading to the initiation of cracks within the concrete matrix [1][2].

In this study, we investigated a self-healing concrete produced with commercially manufactured bacteria as healing agent exposed to freezing and thawing conditions with de-icing salts. The study presents the influence of the exposed conditions through permeability tests, microscopic investigation, scaling analyses, and chloride penetration.

Materials and methods

Self-healing mechanism. The healing agent is available in powder form and is a commercial product composed of bacterial spores (*Bacillus cohnii*) and calcium lactate as carbon source. Both are encapsulated through the extrusion of the carbon sources and the bacterial spores followed by grinding of the extrudate. The pellets have dimensions less than 2 mm. The bacteria-based concrete, depending on the dosage of the healing agent, has the ability to heal cracks up to 0.8 mm under laboratory

conditions [5]. The recommended healing agent dosage is 5-15 kg/m³ concrete. This study investigates a dosage of 10 kg/m³.

Concrete specimens. Self-compacting concrete with a water-to-cement (W/C) ratio of 0.45 was used. It respects the maximum W/C required by EN-206 1 [6] for freeze-thaw attack with de-icing salt in high water saturation, considering XF4 being the exposure class. A concrete with high strength and flow was chosen to achieve better resistance and to allow to distinguish the improvement provided by the use of the healing agent. The concretes contained per m³ 853 kg sand 0/4, 263 kg gravel 2/8, 434 kg gravel 8/16, 360 kg CEM I 52.5 N, 240 kg limestone filler, 162 kg water and 3.22 kg superplasticizer. The content of the healing agent was 10 kg/m³. The concrete had a slump class SF2 and the average 28-day compressive strength was 80 MPa with 2.97 MPa of standard deviation for the reference concrete, and 71 MPa with 3.02 MPa of standard deviation for bacterial concrete. The geometry of the cast cylindrical specimens is 100 mm in diameter and 50 mm in height. After casting, the specimens were stored in an air-conditioned room with a temperature of 20±2 °C and a relative humidity of at least 95% for 24 hours. Subsequently, samples were demoulded and placed in this room until 28 days. At this age cracks were created in part of the specimens. Realistic cracks were made by the Brazilian splitting test producing average crack widths of 170±50 µm. After crack creation, the specimens were submerged in water with the cracks that would be exposed facing downwards for 28 days to allow healing. The uncracked specimens were placed in the same conditions as the cracked concrete samples.

Crack width measurements. The crack width of realistic cracks was measured at eleven places along the crack length at the top side with three measurements performed on each image. The measurements were executed with a stereomicroscope, Leica S8 APO with DFC 295 camera. The locations were fixed to allow analysis of the same place after exposure. In order to do so, a 3D printed template was used with some tag points. This method was used instead of a method where marks are applied on the samples surface to indicate crack measurement locations as the surface could be destroyed during the freeze-thaw cycles.

Freeze-thaw with de-icing salts. The experiment was based on the standard CEN/TS 12390-9 [7]. For the uncracked concrete the standard was followed. However, for the cracked concrete samples some adaptations to the standard were required. The protection of the crack is the most important factor, as one of the steps in the experiment is to glue the specimen into a PVC tube of 70 mm in height and 110 mm in internal diameter. The procedure is to fill the gap between the specimen and the wall of the PVC tube with epoxy resin with a low viscosity (Figure 1a). If the crack is not well protected, the epoxy resin may enter the crack filling part of it. The way to avoid this is to protect the crack by a tape with a high adherence. Aluminium tape was used at the locations where the tape did not have to be removed after the test (Figure 1b). The bottom of the specimens used for the water permeability test was sealed with white masking tape (Figure 1c), and then aluminium butyl tape on top to avoid leakage during the freeze-thaw test (Figure 1d). Finally, the specimens were placed into an insulating material (Figure 1e), covered with the chloride solution, protected with a resistant plastic, and inserted into a freeze-thaw chamber.

Figure 1. Concrete specimens glued into a PVC tube (a), the aluminium tape protecting the crack before gluing into a PVC tube (b), the white masking tape protecting the crack allowing removal after exposure at the bottom of the specimen (c), aluminium butyl tape placed on the bottom to avoid leakage during the test where the specimen is shown upside down (d), and insulation system applied while testing in the freeze-thaw chamber (e)

Self-healing efficiency. The water flow test with a constant water head (25 cm) was used to assess the permeability, hence, the self-healing efficiency. A method similar to the one of Shin et al. [8] was used. The permeability was measured at the time of crack creation, after healing, and after freeze-thaw exposure. Three specimens were used for each combination for water flow test. Microscopic images were collected at each time step using the same microscope as the one used to measure the crack widths. The collection of scaled material was performed at time steps as specified in the standard CEN/TS 12390-9 [7]. To collect the scaled material from the test surface, the surface was rinsed with demineralized water using a spray bottle. The brush as recommended by the standard was avoided because the formed healing products could be destroyed, affecting the results. The chloride penetration was measured perpendicular to the crack, after splitting the specimens, at the end of the freeze-thaw

cycles . Once the surface was dry, a 0.1 mol/L silver nitrate solution was sprayed on the fractured cylinder halves to visualize the chloride ingress. The location of the colour change boundary was measured from the top every 5 mm for cracked concrete, and every 10 mm for uncracked concrete by discarding 10 mm from the edges. The entrance through the crack horizontally was quantified in the middle of the specimen height.

Results and discussion

Crack healing efficiency after exposure. The self-healing efficiency was quantified by performing a water flow test (Figure 2a) before (28 d) and after the healing period (56 d), as well as after the freeze-thaw exposure (112 d) . Both the reference (REF) and bacterial (BAC) concretes showed a reduction in the permeability after the healing period demonstrating sealing capacity. Likewise, both concretes showed significant healing during freeze-thaw exposure. The REF concrete was sealed for 78% after the healing period in case of specimens with an average crack width of $175 \mu\text{m} \pm 31 \mu\text{m}$, and nearly 100% after freeze-thaw exposure. In contrast, the BAC concrete sealed for 70% in case of specimens with an average crack width of $163 \mu\text{m} \pm 37 \mu\text{m}$, and 93% after exposure. Although the BAC concrete had a lower average crack width, it showed somewhat lower healing efficiency in the water flow test, probably because of the parallel-walled crack that permitted leaching forming weak stalactites. The method used for crack creation generates through-going cracks, and differences in the crack width on both surfaces are unavoidable. Despite the fact that the crack width is on average similar on both surfaces, generally, the width at the top surface is slightly different from the width at the bottom surface. These variations cause variability in the water flow test, although the mean value of different specimens is the same.

Figure 2. Water flow rate (a). Crack images for reference concrete with $220 \mu\text{m}$ of width (b) at the crack creation day, (c) after healing period, (d) after exposure to freeze-thaw cycles, and for bacterial concrete with $215 \mu\text{m}$ of width (e) at the crack creation day, (f) after healing period, (g) after exposure to freeze-thaw cycles. The scale bar represents 1 mm.

Cracks that cross the specimen increase the leaching of calcium hydroxide on the bottom surface combined with the intense production of calcium carbonate from the bacteria. In addition, the gravity in a submerged condition contributed to the production of a huge amount of healing product in the crack surface facing downwards. These factors caused formation of stalactites along the crack (Figure 2f). The stalactites did not have resistance enough to survive the water flow test and some small holes were created at the location of the stalactites needles. The holes allowed the water to cross the crack, increasing the permeability. On the other hand, REF concrete did not demonstrate crack closure as shown by microscopic analysis (Figure 2c). Further research should focus on samples located in a wet environment with flexural cracks, as it is expected that the tendency for stalactite formation of the BAC concrete will be lower. Note that the healing product was damaged due to freezing as observed in the microscopic analyses (Figure 2g).

Resistance of autonomously healed concrete to scaling and chloride penetration. The scaling results after 56 days are given in Figure 3a. The BAC concrete decreased the scaling by $89\% \pm 3.2\%$ for uncracked concrete, and $91\% \pm 2.3\%$ for cracked concrete compared to the REF concrete. For the REF uncracked concrete, scaling was reduced by $25\% \pm 2.9\%$ compared to the REF cracked concrete, while for the BAC uncracked concrete it was reduced by $12\% \pm 1.7\%$ compared to the BAC cracked concrete. Therefore, the BAC concrete increases the resistance to scaling, reducing significantly damage caused by loss of material due to freezing. The small difference in the scaling between uncracked concrete and cracked concrete, for REF and BAC concretes, shows that there was not only an increase in the surface strength of the material but a widespread improvement in resistance throughout the sample. Chloride penetration has also been reduced for BAC concrete, both uncracked and cracked (Figure 3c and Figure 3e), compared to REF concrete (Figure 3b and Figure 3d). The BAC uncracked concrete decreased the chloride penetration by 46% compared to the REF uncracked

concrete. The BAC cracked concrete decreased the chloride penetration from the surface by 35% compared to the REF cracked concrete. The horizontal penetration by the crack did not show a significant difference between both concretes, but depends largely on the crack widths as well as the internal crack geometries. The improvements in the resistance to scaling and chloride penetration generated by the use of self-healing concrete produced with bacteria are possibly due to a densification of the concrete or due to changes in the porosity increasing the air-entrainment in the bacterial concrete. This is currently further investigated.

Figure 3. Scaling under freeze-thaw with de-icing salts (a). Depths of chloride penetration with gray colour representing the area with chlorides for uncracked reference concrete (b), uncracked bacterial concrete (c), cracked reference concrete (d), and cracked bacterial concrete (e)

Conclusion

The bacterial concrete showed better performance under freezing and thawing conditions. There are two possible hypotheses (1) the densification due to the healing products increased the resistance of the concrete, or (2) the healing agent induced a microstructure with greater distribution and amount of porous, that is, bringing the benefits of the air-entrainment. Further studies need to be done to understand the actual factors. The freeze-thaw condition contributes to the internal healing measured by water permeability; however, chloride penetration through the crack cannot be prevented. The generated healing products in the crack were damaged by scaling due to freezing during the exposure period. Although the bacteria have less or no proven efficiency at low temperatures, cycles between low and high temperatures may have contributed to the reactivation of spores in periods of positive temperature. While in freezing conditions, they may regress to spores to survive for the next activation period. Although, the healing period may have contributed to the good performance of the bacterial concrete.

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